

A CASE REPORT ON APPENDICULAR MASS

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Abstract: Appendicular mass is a complication of delayed or untreated acute appendicitis, presenting as a localized inflammatory lump in the right iliac fossa. This case involved a 35-year-old female who presented with abdominal pain for 10 days and associated fever. Clinical findings and laboratory investigations, including mild anemia and neutropenia, supported the diagnosis. The condition develops as a protective response, where the inflamed appendix is surrounded by adjacent structures such as the omentum, ileum, and cecum, limiting the spread of infection. The patient was managed conservatively with intravenous fluids, broad-spectrum antibiotics, analgesics, and supportive care. Close monitoring showed gradual clinical improvement, with resolution of the mass over time. An interval appendectomy is planned to prevent recurrence. This case emphasizes the significance of early recognition and timely management of appendicular mass to avoid complications such as abscess, peritonitis, and sepsis, while highlighting the effectiveness of conservative treatment in stable patients.

Keywords: Neutropenia, Omentum, Sepsis.

1. INTRODUCTION:

APPENDIX: It is a small, narrow, finger-shaped tube attached to the cecum, which is the first part of the large intestine. It is located in the lower right side of the abdomen. It also contains lymphoid tissue.

Size: 5-10cm long; 5-8mm diameter.

Functions: Although earlier it was thought to be vestigial organ (no function) now several uses are known; Immune function, Reservoir of good bacteria, Digestive support.

APPENDICITIS: It is an inflammation of the appendix usually caused by the obstruction of the appendiceal lumen by fecal matter [fecolith], infection or lymphoid hyperplasia.

APPENDICULAR MASS: Is a localized inflammatory swelling formed when the inflamed appendix is surrounded by omentum and nearby intestinal loops, preventing spread of infection.

APPENDICULAR ABSCESS: Is a collection of pus around the appendix due to perforated appendicitis.

2. SUBJECTIVE EVIDENCE

A female patient of age 35 years old came to hospital and admitted in general medicine ward with chief complaints of pain in abdomen since 10 days (squeezing type of pain) and fever.

PMHx: 1.pint PRBC transfusion at 5 years ago ;2 LSCS at 16 years ago and 14 years ago ; LMP with 3 days flow and cycle is normal i.e., 28 days.

3. OBJECTIVE EVIDENCE

HEMATOLOGY :

Haemoglobin: 9.1*g/dl.

White blood cells: 9800/UL.

Red blood cells: 3.8million cells /UL.

Platelets: 3.11 lakhs/cubic mm.

Serum creatinine: 0.6 mg/dl.

DIFFERENTIAL LEUCOCYTE COUNT :

Neutrophil: 77%.

Lymphocytes: 16*%.

Monocytes: 06%.

Eosinophil: 01%.

Basophils: 00*%.

4. ASSESSMENT

Based on the subjective and objective evidence the patient was diagnosed as "APPENDICULAR MASS".

DISEASE PROFILE :

An appendicular mass is a localized inflammatory lump formed in the right iliac fossa due to acute appendicitis , usually when diagnosis and treatment is delayed(48-72hrs).

FORMATION :

It develops when the inflamed appendix becomes walled off by,Omentum,Ileum,cecum,parietal peritoneum. This is the body's defence mechanism to prevent spread of infection.

TYPES

1. Appendiceal masses are broadly classified into non-neoplastic inflammatory masses (phlegmon or abscess due to acute appendicitis) and neoplastic tumours.
2. Neoplastic types include ;Neuroendocrine tumours(carcinoids),Mucinous neoplasms (LAMN/HAMN),Adeno carcinomas and Goblet cell carcinoids.

These can be benign or malignant, often discovered incidentally.

EPIDEMIOLOGY

- Appendicular mass is a complication of acute appendicitis that develops when treatment is delayed.
- Occurs in about 2–6% of patients with acute appendicitis.
- Common in young adults (10–40 years).
- Can occur in children and elderly.
- Elderly patients have higher risk of complications.
- Slightly more common in males than females.
- Male : Female ratio \approx 1.2 : 1.

AETIOLOGY

- Untreated or delayed acute appendicitis (after 48-72hrs).
- Perforated appendix that gets walled off locally.
- Severe inflammation of appendix leading to local adhesions.
- Body's defense mechanism -omentum and bowel loops. surround the inflamed appendix to limit infection.

PATHOPHYSIOLOGY

- Luminal obstruction of appendix.

[causes: fecolith, lymphoid hyperplasia, parasites, foreign body].

- Continued mucus secretion

[Increased intraluminal pressure].

- Venous congestion and ischemia

[impaired blood flow to appendiceal wall].

- Bacterial overgrowth

[common organisms:E.coli,Bacteroids

fragilis].

- Acute inflammation of appendix.

[Oedema,wall thickening,risk of perforation].

- Local perforation or severe inflammation.

[Infection tends to spread locally].

- Protective localization

[Omentum, cecum, ileum and peritoneum surround the inflamed appendix].

- Inflammatory adhesion formation.

[Resulted in a palpable inflammatory mass]

SIGNS AND SYMPTOMS

Pain in right lower abdomen, Fever, Tender, palpable mass in Right iliac fossa, Reduced bowel sounds, Anorexia, Nausea.

COMPLICATIONS

Appendicular abscess, Generalized peritonitis, Sepsis, Recurrent appendicitis.

PLAN

STANDARD THERAPY

1. Conservative management :

- Nil by mouth.
- IV fluids to maintain hydration.
- Broad spectrum IV antibiotics to cover gram negative and anaerobes.
eg:1.Ceftriaxone-Metronidazole. 2.Piperacillin-Tazobactam. 3.Amoxicillin-Clavulanate.
- Analgesics (paracetamol +opioid.
- Anti emetics.
- Close monitoring of vitals, abdominal signs, WBC count.
- Mass resolve in 2-3 weeks.

2. Interval appendectomy :

- performed 6-8 weeks.
- Prevents recurrence.
- Done once inflammation subsides

3. Management of appendicular abscess:

If abscess is suspected or confirmed:

- USG/CT guided percutaneous drainage.
- Continue IV antibiotics.
- Emergency surgery if: Rupture. Worsening abscess. Failure of conservative treatment.

4. When immediate surgery is indicated :

- Generalized peritonitis.
- Intestinal obstruction.
- Failure of conservative Therapy.
- Diagnostic uncertainty.

CURRENT THERAPY

BRAND NAME	GENERIC NAME	DOSE, ROUTE AND FREQUENCY	CATEGORY	DURATION
1.Inj.Monocef	Ceftriaxone	1gm/IV/BD	Antibiotic	5-7days
2.Inj.Metrogyl	Metronidazole	500mg/IV/TID	Antibiotic	5-7days
3.Inj.Dynapar	Diclofenac	75mg/IM or IV/BD or SOS	NSAID	3-5days
4.Inj.Pan	Pantoprazole	40mg/IV/OD	PPI	5-7days
5.Inj.Zofer	Ondansetron	4mg/IV/BD	Anti emetic	2-3days
6.Ivf.NS	Normal saline	100cc/hr	IV fluid	2-3days
7.Ivf.RL	Ringers lactate	100cc/hr	IV fluid	2-3days
8.Ivf.DNS	Dextrose normal saline	100cc/hr	IV fluid	2-3days
9.Inj.Buscopan	Hyoscine butyl bromide	20mg/IV/BD	Anti spasmotic	3-5days

PATIENT COUNSELLING**ABOUT THE DISEASE**

An appendicular mass is a localized inflammatory lump formed in the right iliac fossa due to acute appendicitis, usually when diagnosis and treatment is delayed(48-72hrs).Treatment is mainly with medications and rest to reduce inflammation.

ABOUT THE MEDICATION

NBM initially to rest the bowel.

IV antibiotic are given to control infections.

IV fluids are given to prevent dehydration.

Diclofenac is given to reduce discomfort /pain .

Complete the full course of antibiotics.

Do not skip doses.

Avoid alcohol while on metronidazole.

LIFESTYLE MODIFICATION

Eat light , easily digestible foods (rice , curd)

Avoid spicy , oily, junk foods and alcohols.

Take adequate bed rest during acute phase.

Avoid heavy lifting, strenuous activity.

Resume normal activities gradually after recovery.

DRUG INDUCED APPENDICULAR MASS

Drug-induced appendicular mass is rare. Drugs such as opioids, anticholinergics, corticosteroids, and NSAIDs may indirectly contribute by causing constipation, immunosuppression, or intestinal inflammation leading to appendicitis.

CONCLUSION

Appendicular mass is a significant complication of delayed acute appendicitis that requires timely recognition and appropriate management. This case demonstrates that conservative treatment with intravenous antibiotics, fluids, and supportive care is effective in stable patients, leading to resolution of the inflammatory mass. Careful monitoring is essential to detect any progression to complications such as abscess formation, peritonitis, or sepsis. The role of interval appendectomy remains important in preventing recurrence once the acute inflammation subsides. Overall, early diagnosis, rational antibiotic use, and individualized treatment planning play a crucial role in improving patient outcomes and reducing morbidity associated with appendicular mass.

REFERENCE

- 1.Rajah KH ,Appendicular Phlegmon: Current Management, European Journal of Medical and Health Research.
2. National institute of health.
- 3.Forsyth J, The evolving management of the appendix mass in the era of laparoscopy and interventional radiology. The Surgeon, 2017.
- 4.Garba ES, Ahmed A ,Management of Appendiceal Mass. Annals of African Medicine, 2008.
- 5.International Journal of Academic Medicine and Pharmacy (www.academicmed.org).
- 6.Satheesh Kumar M ,Abdul Saleem M ,Evaluating Management Strategies for Appendicular Mass ,Journal of Gastrointestinal Surgery.
- 7.Kumar Hari Rajah ,Somanathan Menon ,Current Management Of Appendicular Mass - A Narrative Review.

8. Bhangu A, Acute Appendicitis: Modern Understanding of Pathogenesis, Diagnosis and Management, 2015.

9. Bailey & Love's Short practice of Surgery, 28th Edition, 2018.

10. Kumar V, Abbas Ak, Aster JC; Robbins & Cotran pathologic basis of disease, 10th Edition, 2020.